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CLICHÉ EXPRESSIONS (“KALIP SÖZLER”) AS A MANIFESTATION OF THE ETHNOMENTAL DIVERSITY OF THE POLITENESS CATEGORY (IN THE CONTEXT OF TURKISH COMPLEX SENTENCES)

The article deals with the issue related to the problem of the Turkish compound sentence. It turns out that the Turkish complex sentence is forced to “complicate” its original simple format due to the requirements of the courtesy rules. That is, the same intention is expressed more politely, unobtrusively. In this sense, Turkish patterns of compound sentences can be compared to the category of politeness in Japanese and Korean. It is known that the keigo system manifests itself both at the lexical and grammatical levels. On some points, the principle of politeness, which is syntactically resolved in Turkish complex sentences, shows commonality with keigo.

Keywords: Modern Turkish language, complex sentence problem, cliché expressions (*kalıp sözler*), politeness category, Japanese and Korean languages, *Keigo*.

As is well known, expressions presented under the name “*kalıp sözler*” in Turkish linguistics actually demonstrate an ability to extend beyond the “sphere of influence” of the lexical stratum. In this sense, we can infer that the politeness category, which determines Turkish speech behavior, shares certain features with the politeness category in the Japanese language. As is known, the politeness category in Japanese and Korean does not merely manifest itself at the level of polite language norms defined by speech etiquette rules but constitutes a comprehensive lexical-grammatical category [1]. In both languages, the corresponding lexical and grammatical inventory serves to express politeness concepts that are essential to Japanese and Korean mentalities but often represent cultural lacunae, complicating the translation process for other cultures.

The Japanese politeness category, known as *Keigo*, fully reflects the hierarchical nature and conservative traditionalism of Japanese society, while also clearly illustrating significant differences from the linguistic identity of communities shaped by Western cultural mentalities. As N.T. Khalmuzarova also notes, the *Keigo* system, characterized by lexical-grammatical means, highlights elements such as “politeness, respect, deference, strict adherence to subordination, the speaker’s humility, modesty, attentiveness, the listener’s concentration, and simultaneously, the formality or official nature of relationships” (i.e., the inevitable social distance requirement arising from internal societal hierarchy during communication - J.R.) [2; 83-84].

It should also be noted that, as pointed out by D.A. Kozhevnikova, who analyzed the forms of expression of the politeness category in the Japanese language and highlighted the inevitable difficulties encountered when assimilated by representatives of different cultures, *Keigo* is a category that manifests itself at lexical-grammatical levels. In this context, intra-community social knowledge (information about hierarchy) inevitably emerges as background knowledge, thereby guiding the syntactic constructions in one form or another. The linguist emphasizes that in this case, there is a widespread use of conditional subordinate clauses. Furthermore, D.A. Kozhevnikova draws attention to the

significant role of such expressions in creating negative distancing [4; 325-332].

For comparison, it can be noted that in the Turkish language, complex sentence models with conditional subordinate clauses, expressing excessive politeness, may convey a request, warning, or reprimand from one party to the other, demonstrating negative distancing during the communication process. For instance:

- *"Ben onlardan uzak yaşayamam, kendi çabalarımla iş bulamadım, bana yardımcı olursanız beni çok mutlu edersiniz."* [4]

- *"Evimi de ziyaret ederseniz beni çok mutlu edersiniz."* [5]

In the given examples, when contrasted with “sincere speech acts,” the following examples reveal “insincere speech acts” that serve to express negative distancing (for a more detailed discussion, see [6; 30-37]).

Additional examples include:

- *"Sevgili dostlar, sayfayı beğenmeden yorum beğeni yapmasanız sevinirim, aksi taktirde engellerim."* [7]

- *"Değerli Hanımefendi, genelleme yapmasanız çok sevinirim; zira, Babam Hacı ve bizi Atatürk düşmanı olarak yetiştirmedim."* [8]

If we hypothetically classify world languages into two categories:

1. Languages that manifest the politeness category at all levels of the language system (lexical, morphological, and syntactic), as observed in Japanese and Korean, and

2. Languages that realize politeness concepts to a limited extent (through specific honorifics, communicative markers, etc.) [9; 13], then it can be noted that the Turkish language, with its own set of ritualistic speech habits expressing politeness and its repertoire of routinized politeness expressions, may be positioned closer to Japanese and Korean.

This is because, without familiarity with the expressions presented under the name “*klişe sözler*” and without identifying their constitutive potential, no foreign speaker can establish successful communication within the Turkish community. To substantiate our position, we would like to briefly point out that such situations may lead to communicative failures that can be

termed as “incidents.” Utilizing S. Huntington’s metaphor, it can be argued that in some cases, unfamiliarity with the speech habits shaped by politeness principles of a different culture may result in situations reminiscent of a “clash of civilizations” (an arguably hyperbolic characterization).

An illustrative example of this can be drawn from T.V. Larina’s study titled “Politeness as a Regulator of Communicative Behavior.” During a scientific conference in Moscow, a Korean scholar concluded his presentation with a phrase that, in translation, conveyed the meaning “Forgive me for my limited and uninteresting report” (Простите за мой скудный и безынтересный доклад / Yetersiz ve ilginç olmayan raporum için beni bağışlayın), provoking laughter from the Russian-speaking audience [1]. However, the scholar merely intended to politely conclude his speech in full accordance with the politeness norms of the Korean language.

For comparison, it can be noted that for Turkish speakers, the behavior of a communicator who humbly apologizes for their “scribbles” would not appear surprising. For instance, S.V. Chironov, who has evaluated typical encouraging speech formulas characteristic of Japanese communication strategies, presents several examples that, in the context of Turkish speech etiquette, do not seem “foreign.” One such translated example from Japanese to Turkish reads:

- *"There is nothing to be done, my urgent wish is that any problem in the League of Nations be resolved without obstacles."* [2; 18-32]

Similarly, let us examine the use of analogous speech formulas in Turkish:

- *"Daha önce de söylemiştim ya, Yüce ALLAH kaderini yazıyor, yapacak bir şey yok."* [11]

These formulaic “kلیşe sözler” actually function as ready-made speech formulas within the Turkish community, emerging under the influence of the Turkish-Muslim ethnocultural identity, characterized by belief, fatalism, and a tendency to attribute the course of fate to destiny or divine will. Rather than being dictated, this worldview operates in a “background knowledge” mode, where Turkish speech etiquette formulas eliminate the sense of inevitability, surrendering the flow of life to an invisible force. This mindset results in the frequent use of expressions such as “kısmetse” (if fate allows), “Allah nasip ederse” (if God grants), “yapacak bir şey yok” (there is nothing to be done), “Allah izin verirse” (if God permits), and similar phrases, especially when compared with Azerbaijani expressions like “Allah qoysa” (if God wills).

The reason that compelled the modestly concluding Korean scholar to use the aforementioned phrase similarly pushes Turkish speakers to elaborate their otherwise straightforward remarks with “fatalistic” speech act units. As evident from the examples, responses that could be as simple as “evet/hayır” (yes/no) are often complicated with fatalistic “kلیşe sözler.” This phenomenon occurs because, for a Turkish speaker, such straightforward answers might imply a contradiction to the belief that God is the sole determiner of past, present, and future events.

It should be noted that, as pointed out by İ. Onursal Ayırır, who attempted to clarify the issue from a linguo-pragmatic perspective, “kalıp sözler” (set phrases) are not homogeneous in nature. They can be divided into routine set phrases and expressions, and communicative set phrases and expressions (routine kalıp sözler and konuşma kalıp sözler) [15; 86–98]. In our view, since the former mainly possesses a phraseoreflex nature, they are of lesser interest from the perspective of communicative syntax, specifically in the context of the complex sentence problem.

It should also be noted that the exceptional importance of politeness principles in Turkish linguistic identity and the purposeful use of complex sentence models loaded with relevant set phrases for communicative success (for more on “communicative success,” see [16; 235–236]) can be clearly observed not only through synchronic but also diachronic studies and speech materials. As A. Aydemer notes, the “Divanü Lügati’t-Türk” contains numerous words and expressions highlighting the crucial role of the politeness principle in interpersonal relations [17; 14–36].

According to X. İmamova, the forms of politeness (or, more precisely, the politeness category) in Turkish have both lexical and grammatical characteristics [19; 75]. Although the grammatical manifestations of politeness concepts in Turkish have not been extensively analyzed like Keigo, their existence—particularly their active expression in complex sentence formats—is undeniable.

We must also emphasize that we are far from equating set phrases (kalıp sözler) with speech etiquette formulas. The term “kalıp sözler” in Turkish linguistics encompasses words, phrases, and sentence-based units that embody linguistic elements with extensive structural-semantic and functional diversity. As stated in the research by N. Sis and B. Gökçen, the terms “kalıp sözler” or “ilişki sözler” (i.e., communicative markers) in linguistics (more accurately, in Turkish linguistics) include expressions and proverbs that clearly reflect the customs, lifestyles, and hierarchically structured interpersonal relationships within the speaking community [20; 1979]. Thus, they encompass both ritualistic words and expressions, pre-fabricated phraseoreflexes, as well as address forms for individuals of higher (older or socially superior) or lower (younger or socially inferior) status.

Therefore, it can be argued that “kalıp sözler” constitute a rich linguistic inventory that, when used by different speakers, allows us to identify the realization of these linguistic units within speech etiquette formulas. In other words, in the first case, we encounter a set of linguistic facts existing on the basis of linguistic competence (to use N. Chomsky’s terminology), while in the second case, we observe components of speech acts materializing within concrete speech performances.

In the following example, we encounter the softening of a negative context through the use of the rica ederim set phrase as a complex sentence component. In this case, although the speaker’s intention is directed towards performing warning or critical speech acts, the use of the main clause rica ederim serves as a corrective mechanism to avoid the realization of an illocutionary

breach (“illocutionary misfire”—a concept discussed further below). In other words, speakers, consciously or subconsciously, utilize various speech strategies to maintain a positive self-image during communication, preventing the addressee from being eliminated as a communicative party (i.e., avoiding illocutionary misfire) [21; 14].

Examples include:

- *"Rica ederim, böyle olanlar kendilerinin ne olduklarını ve ecdâdları gibi ne tür hizmetlere imza attıklarını hiç düşünmezler mi?"* [22]
- *"Rica ederim, bir şey söyleme kaybettirsin."* [23]

In these cases, the likelihood of the imperative "Sus" (be silent) leading to an illocutionary misfire necessitated a more polite formulation. As seen, the rica etsem and rica ediyorum components of complex sentences exhibit distinct conventionalized characteristics (apparent only to native speakers or those deeply familiar with the linguistic environment). The rica etsem clause, functioning as the main clause of a conditional subordinate sentence, implicitly expresses deference towards the addressee. In contrast, the rica ediyorum clause in a complement subordinate sentence may serve to convey both positive and implicitly negative information.

Thus, in the first case, we primarily encounter communicative impositivity, while in the second case, we may face communicative situations characterized as insincere speech acts, in addition to communicative impositivity.

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